

An Automated Workflow to Discover the Structure–Stability Relations for Radiation Hard Molecular Semiconductors

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Abstract

Emerging photovoltaics for outer space applications are one of the many examples where radiation hard molecular semiconductors are essential. However, due to a lack of general design principles, their resilience against extraterrestrial high-energy radiation cannot be currently predicted. In this work, the discovery of radiation hard materials is accelerated by combining high-throughput, lab automation and machine learning. This way, a large material library of more than 130 organic hole transport materials is automatically processed, degraded, and measured. The materials are degraded under ultraviolet-C (UVC) light in a nitrogen atmosphere, serving as the conditions for electromagnetic radiation hardness tests. A parameter closely related to the differential quantum yield for photodegradation is extracted from the evolution of the UV–visible (UV–vis) spectra over time and used as a stability target. Following this procedure, a stability ranking spanning over 3 orders of magnitude was obtained. Using Gaussian Process Regression based on predictors derived from structural fingerprints, structure–stability relations for UVC stable materials were identified: fused aromatic ring clusters are beneficial, whereas thiophene, methoxy and vinylene groups are detrimental. The established predictive model quantifies the effect of specific molecular features on UVC stability, allowing chemists to consider UVC stability in their molecular design strategy.

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